

ACTION OF ALKALINE IODINE SOLUTION ON ACETALDEHYDE

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There are two competing reactions taking place, one is iodine substitution resulting in the formation of iodoform and another is oxidation of the aldehyde to acetic acid. Iodoform has been estimated and the presence of acetate ions detected by the lanthanum nitrate method. On diluting the reaction mixture with plenty of water and increasing the alkali concentration, it is possible at low temperatures to convert 98% of the aldehyde to iodoform, whereas under suitable conditions 99% of the aldehyde can be oxidised to acetic acid. There is indication to show that OI^- ions are responsible for iodine substitution and the unionised HOI molecules act as oxidant.

In a quantitative study of this reaction, Hitcher and Mueller (*Trans. Roy. Soc. Canada*, 1929, 3-23, III, 35) reported that under the most favourable conditions it was carried only to 60% of completion. They estimated the amount of iodine consumed and inferred that only iodoform reaction had occurred. Dal Nogare *et al.* (*Anal. Chem.*, 1951, 23, 1473) who extracted the iodoform produced with chloroform and estimated it by finding its absorption at 347 $m\mu$ came to a similar conclusion. Mitchell *et al.* ("Organic Analysis", 1953, Vol. I, p. 268) compared the extents of the reaction by various compounds which produced iodoform with alkaline iodine solution and concluded that in case of acetaldehyde the reaction was not stoichiometrically complete and the conversion to iodoform was the lowest. The present work was undertaken with a view to ascertaining the cause of the low results. It deals specially with the effect of dilution, temperature, alkali concentration and excess of iodine on the course of the reaction which has been studied by determining the amount of iodine consumed and the iodoform produced.

EXPERIMENTAL

A stock solution of 0.05 *M* acetaldehyde was prepared by dissolving a pure sample of the aldehyde in water and standardising it with hydroxylamine sulphate. The procedure followed was that described by Kolthoff and Stenger ("Volumetric Analysis", 1947, Vol. II, p. 224).

Effect of Dilution and Temperature.—Solutions of 0.005 *M* acetaldehyde (5 c.c.) and 0.02*N*-I₂ (10 c.c.) were treated with varying quantities of water and then made to react by adding quickly 4*N*-NaOH solution (5c.c.) with vigorous swirling of the reacting solutions. Three sets of experiments were carried out at 3 different temperatures, viz., to 5°, 20° and 35°. The time allowed for completion of the reaction was 4 to 5 hours at 5°, 1 hour at 20° and ½ hour at 35°. On completion of the reaction, the mixture was acidified with 4*N*-H₂SO₄ (5.5 c.c.) and the iodine liberated was titrated with 0.02*N* hypo solution taken in a 10 c.c. microburette. A blank was carried out similar in all respects except for the addition of acetaldehyde solution, instead of which 200 c.c. of water was used.

With increase in dilution of the reacting solutions, the amount of I_2 consumed was found to increase. Theoretically if all the CH_3CHO were converted to in CHI_3 , each molecule of the aldehyde would consume 6 atoms of I_2 .

At ordinary dilution 3.6 atoms of iodine are consumed per molecule of the aldehyde and this corresponds to 60% reaction reported by previous workers. However, in very dilute solutions it is possible at 5° to convert 98% of the aldehyde in to CHI_3 , as illustrated in Table I.

TABLE I

[0.005M-Acetaldehyde (5 c.c.) + 0.02N- I_2 (10 c.c.) + H_2O + 4N-NaOH (5 c.c.)].

Expt. No.	Water added.	Molality of CH_3CHO in the reaction mixture.	Iodine (g. atom) consumed per molecule of acetaldehyde at		
			5° .	20° .	35° .
1	0 c.c.	12.50×10^{-4}	3.81	3.60	3.51
2	50	3.57	5.00	4.80	4.65
3	100	2.10	5.51	5.40	5.20
4	150	1.47	5.75	5.62	5.43
5	200	1.14	5.88	5.78	5.52
6	250	0.92	5.90	5.75	5.58
7	300	0.78	5.90	5.75	5.60
8	400	0.60	5.90	5.76	5.60

Effect of Alkali Concentration.—The amount of CHI_3 produced was found first to increase with the increase in alkali concentration, but it soon reached a maximum value and with further increase in alkali, the value gradually decreased. The optimum concentration of the alkali, affording the maximum yield of CHI_3 , varied with the concentrations of the CH_3CHO and I_2 solutions. In a series of experiments the same volume of very dilute solution of CH_3CHO and I_2 was treated with 4N-NaOH, varying from 0.1 c.c. to 10 c.c. The amount of I_2 consumed was plotted against the alkali concentration, taken as base. The curve showed a steep rise in the beginning and soon attained a peak, which was flat due to the I_2 consumption remaining the same for a considerable change in the alkali concentration, and later it showed a gradual downward trend.

Effect of Excess of Iodine.—A large excess of iodine was found to afford a lower % conversion of CH_3CHO to CHI_3 , as judged from the amount of I_2 consumed. Table II illustrates the results of experiments carried out at 20° with concentration of all the reactants, except that of I_2 , being kept the same. The alkali added was sufficient to convert all the I_2 into NaOI.

TABLE II

[0.005M-CH₃CHO (5 c.c.) + 200 c.c. water + 0.02N-I₂ soln. + 4N-NaOH (10 c.c.)].

Expt. No.	I ₂ added in excess.	0.02 N-I ₂ consumed.	Expt. No.	I ₂ added in excess.	0.02 N-I ₂ consumed.
1	10%	7.3 c.c.	4	75%	7.1 c.c.
2	25	7.3	5	100	7.1
3	50	7.2	6	200	6.9
Theoretical value (iodoform reaction)					7.5

Iodoform Estimated.—The amount of CHI₃ produced in these reactions was very small and could not be accurately estimated by ordinary methods. A new procedure has been developed the details of which are under publication. The method consists in exposing a solution of CHI₃ in ether-benzene mixture along with 0.01N hypo solution to sunlight for 30-40 minutes with occasional shaking, when the CHI₃ decomposes quantitatively to free I₂, which is estimated by titrating the excess of the hypo solution. Synthetic mixtures of CHI₃ and water were estimated by this method and the error did not exceed 1.0%. In Table III the experimental and the calculated values of CHI₃, obtained from CH₃CHO, are compared. The calculated values have been arrived at by using the formula mentioned in the Discussion.

TABLE III

[0.025M-CH₃CHO (5 c.c.) + water added + 0.05N-I₂ (20 c.c.) + 4N-NaOH (4 c.c.)].

Expt. No.	Water added.	0.05 N-I ₂ consumed.	Iodoform.	
			Found.	Calc.
1	Nil	9.1 c.c.	19.7 mg.	20.2 mg.
2	50 c.c.	11.5	31.5	32.0
3	100	12.7	38.1	38.0
4	150	13.1	39.4	39.9
5	200	13.4	40.1	41.4
6	300	13.9	42.8	43.8

Prevention of Iodoform Formation.—The CHI₃ reaction could be suppressed to a large extent by using about 10% less alkali than the amount required theoretically. To the mixture of acetaldehyde and iodine 1N-NaOH solution was added slowly dropwise from a burette, while the reacting solutions were vigorously shaken with a circular motion. The reactions were carried out at 25-30° and the time allowed for completion was 20 minutes. Later the excess of I₂ was estimated by acidifying the solution with H₂SO₄ and titrating with 0.05N hypo. There was no visible precipitate of CHI₃, but the clear solution possessed a faint smell of it. The minute quantity present was later estimated by photochemical decomposition in sunlight. Assuming that only oxidation of the CH₃CHO molecule takes place, then 2 atoms of iodine will be consumed per molecule of the aldehyde

The experimental and the calculated values of I_2 consumed, recorded in Table IV, compare favourably. Based on these observations, a procedure has been devised for estimating acetaldehyde by oxidising it quantitatively (this *Journal*, 1957, **34**, 739). The presence of acetate ions was detected in the reaction products. After the reaction was over the mixture was treated with excess of alkali and evaporated to dryness for concentrating the acetate ions. The solid residue was treated with a small amount of HCl (conc.) and warmed after adding a few drops of lanthanum nitrate and ammonium hydroxide solutions. I_2 was already present in the solution. A good blue precipitate as described by Vogel ("Qualitative Chemical Analysis", 1948, p. 307) was obtained. The blue colour is said to be due to the adsorption of I_2 on the basic acetate of lanthanum.

TABLE IV

CH ₃ CHO soln. taken (0.05 M).	0.1N-I ₂ added.	NaOH added (1.0N).	0.1N-I ₂ consumed.		CHI ₃ estimated.	CH ₃ CHO converted to CHI ₃ .
			Found.	Calc.		
2 c.c.	10 c.c.	0.9 c.c.	2.05 c.c.	2.0 c.c.	0.4 mg.	1.0%
5	20	1.8	5.05	5.0	0.4	0.4
7.5	30	2.7	7.60	7.5	0.8	0.6
10	40	3.6	10.20	10.0	1.3	0.7
15	75	6.7	15.20	15.0	1.9	0.7
20	100	9.0	20.30	20.0	2.6	0.7

DISCUSSION

It is evident from the data presented above that there are two reactions taking place, one is oxidation of the aldehyde to acetic acid and another is the substitution of I_2 in the aldehyde molecule. The intermediate compound, CI_2CHO , is probably unstable and decomposes readily in presence of alkali to CHI_3 . Woo and Chu (*Science Record*, 1949, **2**, 280) have also stated that the iodoform reaction of CH_3CHO is probably accompanied by oxidation of the molecule.

If the quantity of CH_3CHO is known and the amount of I_2 consumed is determined, then it is possible to calculate the amounts of CHI_3 and acetic acid produced. In the iodoform reaction every molecule of the aldehyde consumes six atoms of iodine whereas in the oxidation reaction, two atoms are consumed. So if x is the fraction of an aldehyde molecule undergoing I_2 substitution, then

$$6x + 2(1-x) = \text{number of I atoms consumed per molecule of } CH_3CHO.$$

Using this formula the amount of CHI_3 produced has been calculated and compared with the experimental values (Table III). The fair agreement between the two shows that the present contention of two simultaneous reactions is correct.

Probable Mechanism of the Reaction.—The reaction of iodine with CH_3CHO to furnish iodoform is probably brought about by OI^- ions, and the oxidation of the aldehyde to acetic acid by the un-ionised molecules of HOI . The following points are adduced in support of this view.

(1) As NaOI is the salt of a very weak acid, it hydrolyses profusely to HOI and NaOH (Ephraim, "Inorganic Chemistry", 1939, p. 351). Hence, in a mixture of I_2 and NaOH, where I_2 is in excess, the concentration of OI^- ions will be very small and therefore such a mixture oxidises 99.3% of the aldehyde, as illustrated in Table IV. Moreover, the presence of OI^- ions cannot be completely eliminated and so the formation of CHI₃ cannot be avoided altogether.

(2) Excess of alkali affects the reaction in various ways. Its actions are summarised below :

On increasing the alkali concentration, the equilibrium of the reaction (i) shifts to the right with the result that more of NaOI is produced. In the same reaction it has been found that even on adding twice the amount of alkali theoretically required, some free I_2 exists as indicated by starch solution, and only after adding ten times the theoretical quantity of alkali all the I_2 is converted in to NaOI. But the velocity of iodination continues to increase with alkali concentration even at this stage when no more of free I_2 exists. This is because OI^- ions, which are responsible for iodination, continue to increase due to the reversal of the reaction (ii) being promoted by the excess of alkali. Lastly alkali tends to retard the iodination process as indicated in reaction (iii). Therefore increase in alkali concentration first accelerates the rate of iodination and later retards it, as found experimentally.

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